

Prevention of Crimes of Sexual Exploitation of Women and Children Through Legal and Criminological Measures

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Abstract. The content of this s article identifies and analyzes the complex of legal and special-criminological measures aimed at preventing the phenomenon of sexual exploitation of women and children. Thus, besides the measures of influence on the economic, political, organizational and legal factors, the authors also note that in the process of preventing this type of criminality it is necessary to focus on the interaction between the governmental and non-governmental structures, the monitoring and the use of the reliable sources of information which characterizes the real situation in the field of reference, as well as on the efficiency of the victim’s prevention system.

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Introduction

In its historical course of development, mankind has used two main ways of counteraction of criminal attacks on the rights and legitimate interests of individuals, society and the state: punishing perpetrators for committing crimes and preventing crime. In recent years, the idea that crime prevention is the most promising way to effectively combat this phenomenon is becoming more and more prominent¹.

Therefore, the prevention activity is examined as a permanent social process, which involves the application of a set of social, cultural, economic, political, administrative and legal measures designed to prevent the commission of antisocial acts, by identifying, neutralizing and eliminating the causes of crime².

At the level of general approach of the investigated subject, it is necessary to take into account the visions of some criminologists exposed in the specialized literature, which set out a box of essential rules the observance of which can ensure the complex prevention of sexual exploitation of women and children. At the same time, this objective can be achieved in terms of general, special and individual prevention, which refers to the main vital spheres and institutions of socialization of the citizen, using the potential of interrelated and interdependent measures of economic, ideological, cultural, legal, organizational-

¹ Carp T. Infrațiunile contra familiei și minorilor și prevenirea lor. Teză de doctor în drept. Chișinău, 2017. P. 115.

² Nistoreanu Gh., Păun C. Criminologie. București: Editura didactică și pedagogică, R.A., 1995. P. 251.

managerial nature, cooperation and coordination of the activity of the subjects involved in the process, as well as the influence on the causes and conditions that generate or favor the commission of this category of crimes³. Traditionally, preventive work and crime prevention measures are divided in two main groups: 1) general and 2) special-criminological.

With regard to the first group of measures, it should be noted that they are applied both for the prevention of crime in general and for the prevention of any other type of crime. Obviously, this category of measures is also very important for the prevention of crimes of sexual exploitation of women and children. At the same time, those measures are not classified as strictly criminological. They are significant not only for certain categories of criminal acts or for crime in general, their area of influence being the whole society. For these reasons, we support the idea that social measures of a general nature, although of a certain criminological importance, do not constitute an exact dimension of the crime prevention system and therefore do not constitute a separate object of study of criminology. Thus, it is about the economic (political), organizational and legal premises (factors) that condition certain transformations in different vital spheres of the state and society.

We remind you that these transformations are also important for the prevention of the crimes we are investigating. However, the preventive role of some actions (measures) does not necessarily imply the actual prevention of crime, because the latter is a well-planned activity, followed by a certain sequence and a well-defined goal. The essence of prevention lies in its orientation on the causes that have generated the commission of crimes and on the potential criminals that are to be prevented from committing crimes. This particular purpose is an essential criterion for differentiating crime prevention from other activities that may have certain preventive effects.

Although our position was set out above, we will continue to use the phrase “general crime prevention measures” for the following reasons. On the one hand, in the analysis of the main measures to prevent crime, including sexual exploitation crimes, both local and foreign specialists include in their structure the complex of general measures of a social nature. On the other hand, the position of scientists is based on the texts of international legal documents, where there is no differentiation of crime prevention measures.

Thus, the constant follow-up of our position and the proper interpretation of the terms and meanings would make it difficult to use the scientific materials published in the literature and the normative acts in the respective field.

³ Противодействие торговле людьми и использованию рабского труда: Научно-практическое пособие. Под общ. ред. Т.В. Пинкевича. Ставрополь: СФ КрУ МВД России, 2008. С. 269.

Therefore, if we refer, for example, to one of the OSCE Action Plans on Combating Trafficking in Human Beings⁴, it lists both measures assigned to the category of general social and special criminological measures, without making any distinction between them. So it's about: 1) measures regarding data collection and research in the field; 2) measures to intensify border control; 3) economic and social strategies to eliminate the main causes of trafficking in human beings and sexual exploitation; 4) public information and awareness measures; 5) legislative measures.

In most international legal documents and recommendations of specialists in the field, there are provisions and approaches aimed at the protection and assistance of victims of sexual exploitation, in connection with which most of the above-mentioned preventive measures are applied. This includes issues of exchange and analysis of information on the most effective forms of assistance to victims of sexual exploitation, the need for special laws to protect victims of sex trafficking, the mechanism of cooperation between States Parties in the transfer and investigation of human trafficking cases, and sexual exploitation, recommendations on the ways of identification and rehabilitation of victims, creation of special shelters and provision of social, legal and medical assistance to victims of sexual exploitation, etc.

This extensive list creates a specific basis for the development of the system of preventive measures for crimes related to the sexual exploitation of women and children, outlining not only the general directions but also the concrete content of those measures. Obviously, in such cases much depends on the approach, the position of the author and the ways identified to solve the problems concerned. For these reasons, there is no single option for developing a system of measures to prevent this category of crime.

It is important to note that the reporting of preventive measures to a particular group is of a relative nature, as, on the one hand, they are interdependent and, on the other hand, the role and nature of their implementation may be different, depending on the subjects of prevention and the scope, the categories of persons to whom it applies, the methods by which the results are obtained, etc. At the same time, these measures are aimed at achieving an essential goal – reducing the number of crimes related to the sexual exploitation of women and children, as well as not admitting or minimizing the negative consequences for the victims of these crimes and for society in general.

Furthermore, we consider it necessary to address in more detail the content and priority directions for the implementation of preventive measures designed to influence the reduction of the phenomenon of sexual exploitation of women and children.

⁴ OSCE Action Plan to Combat Trafficking in Human Beings. Decision No. 557, 24 July 2003. In: <https://www.osce.org/actionplan?download=true>

Measures aimed at eliminating or reducing the negative influence of the main causes of sexual exploitation of women and children

There is an unquestionable need to stabilize the socio-political situation, optimize the socio-economic environment, reduce the level of unemployment and poverty, ensure adequate social protection for the most vulnerable social strata, etc.

In this context, it is important to note that the combination of the explosion of poverty, unemployment, changing social control system, the sudden opening to the West, the privatization of the economy had direct and indirect consequences that led to a worsening of the way women are treated in certain social contexts. Thus, the privatization of the economy has determined, as a side effect, the development of specific characteristics of “wild” capitalism, being reported cases in which women are the favorite victims of a wide range of abuses. The new power relations have not been correlated and counterbalanced with social protection measures and the proper functioning of the administration and justice. The social stress generated by low incomes, unemployment, the risks involved in the new economic system have increased the level of aggression and social violence, and women have attracted the accumulated aggression like a magnet⁵. All this has led, among other things, to the massive involvement of women and children in human trafficking and their sexual exploitation.

Therefore, we find that the category of measures targeted is the basis of any action to prevent antisocial phenomena and crime, including those planned and implemented in order to solve global problems of society, conditioned by its natural development needs. Such a nature of prevention measures predetermines their significant importance in solving the problems of crime in general and crimes related to the sexual exploitation of women and children in particular. These measures include: “...state and social support of the socially vulnerable sections of the population; developing and implementing an effective socio-economic policy, including meeting the interests and needs of women and children in general and vocational training, culture, leisure, technical and technological re-equipment of enterprises and reducing the share of unskilled labor of women; improvement of employment services for the population; creating a well-organized system for training and retraining staff and raising their qualifications; small and medium business development that provides the population with new jobs”⁶.

The activity of preventing crime related to the sexual exploitation of women and children must include those areas of social life in which negative personality qualities are formed in relation to which they often commit crimes. First of all, these are the living and working conditions. In addition to the

⁵ Dragomir Mariana-Cristina. *Criminalitatea feminină. Teză de doctor în drept*. Chișinău, 2014. P. 83.

⁶ Сильков Д. *Преступность женщин: состояние, причины и предупреждение (региональная характеристика)*. Автореферат диссертации кандидата юридических наук. Иркутск, 2003. С. 17.

influence on criminogenic factors, in each of the mentioned areas the society must tend towards a certain harmonization of the roles. Fulfillment of roles should not exclude or hinder the fulfillment of its obligations in another area. It is contraindicated, for example, that overcrowding at work impedes the care of children or the necessary rest. Solving these problems is difficult because they are related to the global problems of the society, the general development of the country and the modification of many deep-rooted concepts. However, without their solution it is not possible to effectively prevent the victimogenic behavior of women and children, as well as criminal activity in general.

Improving the legislative process for measures to prevent and combat trafficking in human beings and their sexual exploitation

In our view, this category of measures involves a broad approach to issues related to various areas. This is, first of all, the Law on Preventing and Combating Trafficking in Human Beings⁷, which was adopted by the Parliament of the Republic of Moldova on 20.10.2005. This official document describes the basic concepts, the object of regulation and the principles of organizing the fight against the targeted phenomenon, the institutional framework, the attributions of public authorities and law enforcement bodies, as well as the activity of non-governmental organizations in preventing and combating trafficking in human beings, including special principles for preventing and combating child trafficking, protection and assistance to victims, limits on liability for trafficking in human beings, international cooperation in the field, etc.

Particularly relevant are the provisions governing the main directions of prevention and combating trafficking in human beings, including sexual exploitation. In this regard, the Government periodically approves, every two years, a National Plan, which must provide for the implementation of complex actions and the implementation of socio-economic initiatives aimed at preventing and combating the phenomenon, as well as the protection of victims of trafficking in human beings, including collaboration with international organizations, non-governmental organizations, other institutions and civil society representatives. Also, the central and local public administration authorities with responsibilities in the field of preventing and combating trafficking in human beings are obliged to adopt their own action plans for the implementation of the National Plan in their fields of activity.

Coordination of the activity of preventing and combating trafficking in human beings, cooperation of public administration authorities with international organizations, non-governmental organizations, other institutions and representatives of civil society is carried out by the National Committee for

⁷ Lege privind prevenirea și combaterea traficului de ființe umane nr. 241-XVI din 20.10.2005. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova nr. 164-167/812 din 09.12.2005.

Combating Trafficking in Human Beings. The respective National Committee has a series of attributions, among which we highlight the most important ones: a) presents to the Government proposals on the bases of the state policy in the field of preventing and combating trafficking in human beings and recommendations aimed at improving the activity of detecting and liquidating the causes and conditions that contribute to the occurrence of trafficking in human beings and to the activities of trafficking in human beings; b) controls the implementation of the National Plan and the execution of legislation to prevent and combat trafficking in human beings by state organizations and institutions, presents information to the Government on how to implement the National Plan; c) collects and analyzes information on the size, status and trends of human trafficking at the national level; d) submits forward proposals to improve legislation to prevent and combat trafficking in human beings and to protect victims of trafficking; e) organizes campaigns to inform the population about the problems of human trafficking and the social danger of this phenomenon; f) coordinates the activity of the territorial commissions for combating trafficking in human beings and of the specialized institutions regarding the realization of the National Plan and the fulfillment of the actions for the prevention and combating of the trafficking in human beings, etc.

In order to coordinate the activity of preventing and combating trafficking in human beings, in the districts, municipalities and in the Autonomous Territorial Unit of Gagauzia, in addition to the executive bodies of the respective representative authorities, territorial commissions are created to combat trafficking in human beings. In Chisinau, such commissions are also created within sectors.

With regard to the competent law enforcement bodies with rights and obligations in the field of preventing and combating trafficking in human beings, an essential role belongs to the Ministry of Internal Affairs and its central and territorial subdivisions, the General Prosecutor's Office and the Intelligence and Security Service.

Thus, MIA: a) carries out activities to prevent and combat trafficking in human beings through the prevention, detection and prosecution of crimes related to trafficking in human beings, in accordance with the legislation in force, conducting criminal prosecution in criminal cases of trafficking and other related actions; b) provides, upon request, physical protection of the victim of trafficking in human beings during the criminal trial, provides other protection and assistance according to the legal provisions. Also, through its bodies specialized in preventing and combating trafficking in human beings, it carries out operative activities of investigation, prosecution, international cooperation, identification and protection of victims of trafficking in human beings, analysis and information, stimulates the creation of zonal centers for preventing and combating trafficking in human beings.

Very important and useful are the legal provisions that directly stipulate the obligation of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, together with the General Prosecutor's Office, to carry out studies to detect and eliminate the causes and conditions that favor human trafficking and to publish every six months in the media statistical information and analysis reports on preventing and combating trafficking in human beings and protecting its victims. It should be noted that this official regulation has as main objective the promotion of the process of study and theoretical-practical analysis of the investigated phenomenon, including the factors that influence human trafficking for sexual exploitation of women and children as the most vulnerable social strata. In turn, these studies are particularly important for the development of measures to prevent and combat trafficking in human beings.

At the same time, the General Prosecutor's Office, within the limits of its competence, carries out activities to prevent and combat trafficking in human beings in accordance with the legislation in force, coordinates, conducts and prosecutes cases related to such trafficking, represents the accusation, on behalf of the state, in court, supervises the observance of human rights, including victims of trafficking, takes other necessary measures in the field. A subdivision specialized in preventing and combating trafficking in human beings has been created within the General Prosecutor's Office.

The Intelligence and Security Service, including its territorial bodies, carries out activities to prevent and combat trafficking in human beings through the detection of links between international organizations and organized criminal groups with traffickers in human beings, as well as through other activities carried out within its competence.

In addition to the law, criminal law has made an essential contribution to preventing and combating the crimes of sexual exploitation of women and children. Although the current Criminal Code is largely in line with international standards, there are some issues that are not well regulated in terms of the involvement of minors in the practice of prostitution. Thus, art. 208² of the current Criminal Code only partially meets the normative requirements that would help in combating the phenomenon of child prostitution, as it establishes criminal liability only for the profit, against any material benefits, of sexual services provided by a person known to be under the age of 18. Regarding the incitement or determination to prostitution or the facilitation of the practice of prostitution, or the profiting from the practice of prostitution by a person known with certainty to be under the age of 18, if the act does not meet the elements of child trafficking, it is not criminalized in the criminal law, which is an impediment in combating such manifestations.

For the stated reasons, in order to fill this legislative vacuum, we propose to complete paragraph 2 of art. 220 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Moldova with letter b¹) "concerning a minor".

It is also important to note that measures aimed at improving legislation should cover all aspects of the legal regulation of various activities, including those that may have links to illegal activities in the field of sexual exploitation. It is about the contravention legislation, in the field of migration, the legislation that regulates the labor or family relations, etc.

Therefore, the imperfection of the contravention legislation that refers to the liability of the persons who obtain profit from prostitution, of the labor legislation that favors the illegal use of the labor force, etc., contributes to the development of negative trends in this type of crime. Therefore, the implementation of measures to overcome legislative collisions and gaps, as well as the optimization of the mechanism of application of legislative acts in the field will adequately reduce the level of sexual exploitation of women and children.

The recommendations of the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe to its Member States in the field of preventing and combating trafficking in human beings, prostitution and other forms of sexual exploitation, especially with the involvement of minors, are also welcome. Thus, the Member States of the European Union are advised to: a) promote the systematic monitoring of the clients of minors who practice prostitution; b) prohibit juvenile prostitution (it does not matter whether or not the minor has given his or her consent to prostitution); c) develop a clear policy on voluntary prostitution by adults; d) avoid double standards and policies that require prostitutes to engage in prostitution illegally⁸.

They must also create more alternatives for prostitutes through the prism of: a) elaboration and development of programs designed to provide prostitutes with the necessary assistance in order to refrain from practicing prostitution; b) solving the problems related to the vulnerability of prostitutes-victims: mental problems, low self-esteem level, childhood abuse, drug use, etc.; c) poverty eradicating, gender inequality, developing opportunities for education and training, etc.; d) ensuring to an appropriate extent the independence of prostitutes in order to impose requirements on clients relating to protected sex; e) respect for the rights of prostitutes, including the right to freely choose whether or not to be a prostitute; f) elaboration of national vocational training programs⁹.

It should be noted that sexual exploitation, especially when children become victims, is closely linked to the moral state of society, the criteria for which sexual promiscuity and the prevalence of sexual offenses against children are considered.

⁸ Parliamentary Assembly. Doc. 11352, 9 July 2007. Prostitution – which stance to take? Report Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men. In: <http://assembly.coe.int/Main.asp?link=/Documents/WorkingDocs/Doc07/EDOC11352.htm>

⁹ Ibidem.

In the last period of time, the phenomenon of pedophilia is becoming more widespread, there is a massive increase in the number of sexual crimes committed against children, the fact of involving minors in prostitution and child pornography is intensifying.

Although some states have criminalized pedophilia as a crime, the medical literature states that it is defined as an “intense and recurrent sexual interest in children at puberty and a disorder that causes a person suffering or interpersonal difficulties or if the person acts in his own interests”¹⁰.

Usually, pedophilia itself is not punished by law, because the concrete facts are punished and not the sensations, feelings and desires (i.e. sexual orientation). The pedophile will only be punished if he gives in to his primary desires and takes action, the most serious form being sexual abuse of children¹¹. At the same time, not everyone who sexually abuses children is a pedophile, and not all pedophiles sexually abuse children¹².

For these reasons, the state, through its competent bodies, including specialized medical institutions, must take all necessary measures to prevent and effectively combat this phenomenon.

Streamlining measures to prevent sexual exploitation of women and children by increasing the processes of interaction of government structures with non-governmental organizations

As a result of the criminal activity, the fundamental human rights are violated and, therefore, a special role in their protection belongs to the Prosecutor’s Office. By monitoring the observance of human rights and freedoms, the Prosecutor’s Office ensures the rule of law, the consolidation of legality, the protection of the rights and freedoms of the citizen, as well as the legal interests of society and the state.

Measures to protect fundamental human rights and freedoms can be more effective in the context of well-organized cooperation with various ministries and official state structures, such as: Ministry of Internal Affairs, Ministry of Health, Ministry of Labor and Social Protection, Ministry of Education, Culture and Research, Intelligence and Security Service, Office of Migration and Asylum, Customs Service, the health protection bodies and the guardianship and curatorship bodies of the local public authorities, etc.

It is also clear that the permanent exchange of information would have positive effects in the field of combating trafficking in human beings for the purpose of sexual exploitation. Thus, this exchange of information must address issues related to: crime preparation; repression of crimes planned and already

¹⁰ Cum este explicată pedofilia din punct de vedere medical. În: <http://e-sanatate.md/News/3504/cum-este-explicata-pedofilia-din-punct-de-vedere-medical>

¹¹ Pedofilie. În: <https://ro.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pedofilie>

¹² Laws Dr. Richard, William T. O'Donohue. „H. E.Barbaree, M. C.Seto”. Sexual Deviance: Theory, Assessment and Treatment. New-York: Guilford Press, 1997. P. 176.

started by massage parlor owners who commit acts of sexual exploitation of women and children; the actions of traffickers in the process of transporting future victims abroad; registration of false documents and visas; smuggling “live goods” through border crossings; the legality of existing employment companies; the operative reaction of the representatives of various services within the limits of their competencies, etc.

An important role in preventing and combating trafficking in human beings, including acts committed for the purpose of sexual exploitation, belongs to the Center for Combating Trafficking in Human Beings (CCTHB), which integrates the work of specialists from different subdivisions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, Customs Service, Intelligence and Security Service, National Anticorruption Center and the General Prosecutor’s Office. Therefore, CCTHB employees carry out the following activities in the process of preventing and combating the respective type of crime: a) organizes operative investigative measures in order to discover crimes and identify criminals; b) conducts criminal prosecution and evidence administration; c) collaborates with non-governmental and international organizations; d) analyzes the provisions of the legislation in force and submits proposals for its improvement; e) takes measures to collaborate with the media and provide them with some information on the results obtained, etc.

In addition to law enforcement and other state bodies involved in preventing and combating sexual exploitation, non-governmental and public organizations have an important role to play in this area. Victims of sexual exploitation often have more confidence in these non-state structures, most often using the help and services they provide.

Special attention deserves the work of the International Organization for Migration (IOM), which over the last decade has been one of the most active participants in the process of combating illegal migration, while providing assistance to migrants and victims of trafficking in human beings for sexual exploitation. IOM’s activity covers the most diverse fields: analysis of the criminal situation in the field of trafficking in human beings and sexual exploitation, revealing the causes and consequences that occur as a result of committing these crimes, raising public awareness, presenting scientifically substantiated recommendations and providing practical assistance – training and informing law enforcement employees about foreign experience in preventing and combating trafficking and sexual exploitation, providing assistance to migrants and providing protection to victims of sexual exploitation, etc.

Monitoring and use of truthful sources of information that characterize the real situation in the field of sexual exploitation of women and children

This kind of preventive activity of sexual exploitation of women and children is taking place with increasing intensity during the recent years. Thus, the activity of law enforcement agencies in order to discover, repress and investigate crimes in the field of sexual exploitation of women and children, general educational measures carried out by non-governmental and public organizations, including the involvement of media sources, show that at the time society is now well informed about the high level of social danger of the phenomenon of sexual exploitation of women and children.

Therefore, recognizing this activity as satisfactory, we consider it necessary to make more active use of Internet resources, as, on the one hand, a large part of the population makes extensive use of the information resources of this type of media and, on the other hand, criminals also apply modern technologies, especially since most of the pre-crime elements related to sexual exploitation have been placed in the virtual space (recruitment of potential victims through websites, porn industry, sexual “negotiations” with minors in order to determine their sexual contact, etc.).

Victimological prevention of sexual exploitation of women and children

This aspect (victimological) of the prevention of crimes related to the sexual exploitation of women and children is a separate topic of research and, for these reasons, in this compartment we will not address in detail the full range of issues to be addressed. It should also be noted that this type of prevention includes, first and foremost, the discovery, assistance and social rehabilitation of victims who have suffered as a result of sexual exploitation.

It is also important that their legal infantilism be taken into account during the preventive activity of possible victims of sexual exploitation. Usually, most victims do not know enough about their rights, they are convinced that their behavior violates the law, that their behavior is illegal and therefore can not rely on the assistance of official structures, for which reason they do not trust in law enforcement, trying to avoid any contact with them.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the following five main groups of preventive measures of the phenomenon of sexual exploitation of women and children are outlined:

- 1) Eliminating or reducing the negative influence of the main causes of sexual exploitation, in particular: stabilization of the socio-political situation, optimization of the socio-economic environment, limiting the share of unemployment, poverty eradication, solving the problems regarding the employment of the population and increasing the social protection for the most vulnerable social strata;

2) Improving the legislative process for combating trafficking in human beings and their sexual exploitation;

3) Increasing the quality and effectiveness of the processes of interaction of governmental structures and non-governmental organizations in the fight against the phenomenon of sexual exploitation of women and children;

4) Monitoring and use of other sources of truthful information that characterize the real situation in the field of sexual exploitation of women and children;

5) Streamlining the victim prevention system, including working with potential victims, rehabilitation and providing necessary assistance to victims of sexual exploitation, as well as the development of various socio-educational activities for this purpose.

Bibliographical references:

1. Carp T. Infrațiunile contra familiei și minorilor și prevenirea lor. Teză de doctor în drept. Chișinău, 2017. 183 p.
2. Cum este explicată pedofilia din punct de vedere medical. În: <http://e-sanatate.md/News/3504/cum-este-explicata-pedofilia-din-punct-de-vedere-medical>
3. Dragomir Mariana-Cristina. Criminalitatea feminină. Teză de doctor în drept. Chișinău, 2014. 160 p.
4. Laws Dr. Richard, William T. O'Donohue. „H. E.Barbaree, M. C.Seto”. Sexual Deviance: Theory, Assessment and Treatment. New-York: Guilford Press, 1997.
5. Lege privind prevenirea și combaterea traficului de ființe umane nr. 241-XVI din 20.10.2005. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova nr. 164-167/812 din 09.12.2005.
6. Nistoreanu Gh., Păun C. Criminologie. București: Editura didactică și pedagogică, R.A., 1995. 352 p.
7. OSCE Action Plan to Combat Trafficking in Human Beings. Decision No. 557, 24 July 2003. In: <https://www.osce.org/actionplan?download=true>
8. Parliamentary Assembly. Doc. 11352, 9 July 2007. Prostitution – which stance to take? Report Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men. In: <http://assembly.coe.int/Main.asp?link=/Documents/WorkingDocs/Doc07/EDOC11352.htm>
9. Pedofilie. În: <https://ro.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pedofilie>
10. Противодействие торговле людьми и использованию рабского труда: Научно-практическое пособие. Под общ. ред. Т.В. Пинкевича. Ставрополь: СФ КрУ МВД России, 2008. 304 с.

11. Синьков Д. Преступность женщин: состояние, причины и предупреждение (региональная характеристика). Автореферат диссертации кандидата юридических наук. Иркутск, 2003. 22 с.

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Streszczenie. Treść artykułu identyfikuje i analizuje kompleks środków prawnych i specjalno-kryminologicznych mających na celu przeciwdziałanie zjawisku seksualnego wykorzystywania kobiet i dzieci. Tym samym, poza miarami oddziaływania na czynniki ekonomiczne, polityczne, organizacyjne i prawne, autorzy zwracają również uwagę, że w procesie przeciwdziałania tego typu przestępczości konieczne jest skoncentrowanie się na interakcji między strukturami rządowymi i pozarządowymi, monitorowanie i korzystanie z wiarygodnych źródeł informacji charakteryzujących rzeczywistą sytuację w zakresie odniesienia, a także o skuteczności systemu prewencji ofiary.

Zusammenfassung. Der Inhalt dieses Artikels identifiziert und analysiert den Komplex rechtlicher und spezialkriminalologischer Maßnahmen zur Verhinderung des Phänomens der sexuellen Ausbeutung von Frauen und Kindern. So weisen die Autoren neben den Einflussmaßnahmen auf die wirtschaftlichen, politischen, organisatorischen und rechtlichen Gegebenheiten auch darauf hin, dass bei der Prävention dieser Art von Kriminalität das Zusammenspiel zwischen staatlichen und nichtstaatlichen Strukturen, der Überwachung und Nutzung zuverlässiger Informationsquellen, die die reale Situation im Referenzbereich charakterisieren, sowie über die Effizienz des Opferpräventionssystems.

Резюме. Содержание данной статьи определяет и анализирует комплекс правовых и специально-криминологических мер, направленных на предупреждение сексуальной эксплуатации женщин и детей. Таким образом, помимо мер воздействия на экономические, политические, организационно-правовые факторы, авторы также отмечают, что в процессе профилактики данного вида преступности необходимо сосредоточить внимание на взаимодействии государственных и негосударственных структур, мониторинг и использование достоверных источников информации,

характеризующей реальную ситуацию, а также на эффективность системы виктимологической профилактики этого вида преступлений.